

PEDAGOGICAL SCIENCES

ANALYSIS OF THE STATE OF PROFESSIONAL TRAINING OF FUTURE TEACHERS OF FOREIGN LANGUAGES IN INSTITUTIONS OF HIGHER EDUCATION

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ABSTRACT

The purpose of the article is to analyze the state of professional training of future teachers of foreign languages in higher education institutions of Ukraine. Having considered the framework conditions and additional opportunities available in Ukraine for the organization and provision of proper training of future teachers of foreign languages, a study of its condition was conducted by means of a questionnaire of higher education applicants and a survey of teachers. The obtained findings of the study indicate the need to improve the professional training of future teachers of foreign languages in the way of considerable improvement of informing them about the essence and content of professional activity as well as focusing on constant self-development and motivation for personal and professional self-improvement.

Keywords: professional training, readiness, acmeological approach, future teachers of foreign languages, institutions of higher education.

Today's development of society challenges higher education institutions to train competent, highly qualified and competitive specialists, ready to independently and effectively solve problems in their future professional activity, seeking constant self-improvement and self-realization.

The European integration movement of Ukraine and the development of international contacts with foreign countries contribute to increasing the importance of training specialists who know a foreign language. English and German, as the official languages of the EU, are an integral part of the European and world space and contribute to the establishment of international partnership relations.

The training of foreign language teachers in pedagogical institutions of higher education has been reflected in a number of publications (S. Amelina, V. Bezliudna, N. Bidiuk, I. Biletska, I. Bim, H. Bondar, A. Kolisnichenko, O. Mysechko, S. Nikolaieva, S. Shandruk and others).

The issue of professional development of prospective teachers, their mastery of pedagogical technologies has been studied by V. Andrushchenko, I. Bekh, O. Braslavska, M. Chepil, T. Hodovaniuk, O. Hryshkova, V. Kovalchuk, V. Luhovyi, V. Maiboroda, L. Orshanskyi, S. Sovhira, N. Sydorochuk, M. Yevtikh and others.

The purpose of the article is to analyze the state of professional training of future teachers of foreign languages in higher education institutions of Ukraine.

A characteristic feature of the professional training of future teachers of foreign languages at the current stage is primarily the possibility to be guided by All-European recommendations on language education, which are not a standard or curriculum for language learning, but are designed to serve two main purposes. First, to encourage different categories of practitioners in the field of languages, including students themselves, to ponder over the goals of language learning,

progress in this process, self-observation, as well as to make it easier for teachers to communicate with each other and with their students, to help students achieve success. Secondly, as the developers note, the purpose of All-European recommendations on language education is not to give orders or even recommendations to use a certain method, but to present guidelines. A valuable component of the Recommendations is a scale of descriptors of levels of language proficiency, which enables assessment and self-assessment of the progress of language learners in the process of mastering the language and speech knowledge and skills.

For a thorough study of the state of training of future teachers of foreign languages in institutions of higher education based on the acmeological approach, it is important to analyze the educational and professional program "Secondary Education (Language and Literature (English, German))" of a number of pedagogical institutions of higher education in Ukraine. The significance of the conducted analysis is conditioned by the lack of an approved standard of higher education in specialty 014 Secondary Education.

At the current stage, training of future teachers of foreign languages in institutions of higher education is carried out according to educational programs that contain program competencies – integral, general and professional. Integral competence is the ability of an individual to solve complex tasks and practical problems in the field of education, in the teaching of a basic foreign language and literature, a second foreign language, which involves the application of theories and methods of pedagogical science under modern conditions of the organization of the educational process in educational institutions.

Generic competences cover a range of abilities defined by the institutions of higher education selected for analysis, for example: the ones to abstract thinking, analysis and synthesis; to apply fundamental theoretical

knowledge in the practical plane; to communicate in the state language in oral and written forms; to communicate in a foreign language, skills in the effective use of information and communication technologies; to critical analysis and self-criticism; adaptability and implementation of actions in an unforeseen situation; to identify, pose and comprehensively solve problems; to perform professional tasks in a team and autonomously, etc. Moreover, the following ones are also found: the ability to conduct research; the ability to develop and manage projects; the ability to act on the basis of ethical considerations.

The professional competences in the educational programs analyzed by us specify the set of abilities of the future teacher for a certain type of professional activity, for example: the ability to analyze and forecast the educational activity of students, as well as their professional activity; ability of written and oral communication in a foreign language; the ability to apply basic knowledge in the field of pedagogy, philology in practice, the ability to use scientific terminology; the ability to form students' foreign language communicative competence; the ability to plan and organize the educational process and extracurricular activities in a foreign language and related to foreign literature; the ability to conduct lessons and extracurricular activities in a foreign language and related to foreign literature, taking into account the appropriate stage of education, to monitor the results of educational activities of students; the ability to apply professional knowledge and developed practical skills in the field of linguistics, literary studies, methods of teaching foreign languages, cultures and foreign literature, etc. In addition to the above, there are also the following abilities: the one to understand the requirements for activities in the chosen specialty, due to the need to strengthen Ukraine as a democratic and legal state; the ability to organize one's own research and publish its results; the ability to create new educational and methodological materials (if necessary).

The educational achievements of higher education seekers are measured in learning outcomes, which are specified by each higher education institution in its study program in accordance with the educational components that ensure the formation of these outcomes. Summarizing the main common learning outcomes in the educational and professional programs that have been analyzed, we can state that they mostly include the following: assimilation of a set of knowledge and skills necessary for successful professional activity and personal fulfillment; analytical skills of applicants regarding activities within educational institutions; knowledge and skills in the methodology of teaching foreign languages; knowledge of English and German language norms; mastery of the native language; readiness for self-improvement and development of one's abilities and inclinations, as well as realization of one's own creative potential; application of various forms, methods and means of providing educational and methodological activities; the ability to communicate orally and in writing in native and foreign languages; possession and use of information and communication technologies in their activities; the ability to search, process

and use information based on various sources; the ability to adequately assess one's own educational and professional activity; the ability to develop and implement a self-development strategy, etc.

The compulsory and optional components are enlisted in the educational and professional programs. Most of the considered Education and Professional Programs have the following components in common: History of Ukraine, Philosophy, Ukrainian Language, Pedagogy, Psychology, Modern Information Technologies, Practical Course of English language, Practical Course of German Language, Methods of Teaching Foreign languages, Lexicology, Literatures of the Countries whose Languages are Studied, Stylistics, as well as teaching practice in institutions of general secondary education, coursework.

At the same time, there are also such components as Basics of Academic Writing, Human Rights and Civil Society in Ukraine, Inclusive Education, Methodology of Educational Work, Basics of Critical Thinking, Basics of Ecology, Theory and Practice of Translation.

For our research, it is important to analyze the content of educational disciplines of the educational program "Secondary Education (Language and Literature (English, German))" precisely in the context of the acmeological approach.

It has been established that the main purpose of applying the acmeological approach during professional training of future teachers of foreign languages is to reorient the vector of education of higher education students to their achievement of the acme peak in education through self-improvement. Effective teaching of foreign languages in institutions of higher education involves acquiring, first of all, professional and methodical competences, the development of positive motivation in learning and the desire for self-actualization and self-realization (Practical Course of the English Language, Practical Course of the German Language, Practical Grammar of the English Language, Practical Grammar of the German Language, Practical Phonetics of the English Language, Practical Phonetics of the German Language, Methodology of Teaching Foreign Languages, Methodology of Teaching Foreign Languages in Specialized Secondary Education Institutions, teaching and production practices, etc.). The formation of acmeological competence of future teachers of foreign languages is facilitated by the use of acmeological technologies: game, project, use of multimedia and distance learning tools, implementation of integrated classes, etc.

Psychological and pedagogical training of future teachers of foreign languages (it includes such disciplines as Pedagogy, Pedagogy of Specialized Education, Comparative Pedagogy, Pedagogy of Partnership, Basics of Pedagogical Mastery, Psychology, Psychology of Specialized Education, Psychological and Pedagogical Practice, etc.) provides for their acquisition of psychological and pedagogical knowledge and provides opportunities for development of the individuality of each student of higher education as a future teacher, formation of readiness for self-improvement throughout life.

In our opinion, for the appropriate level of pedagogical training applicants in institutions of higher education, the cycle of disciplines of psychological and pedagogical training should include both normative disciplines and disciplines of the variable cycle.

The educational and professional program “Secondary Education (Language and literature (English, German))” of training future teachers of foreign languages, including German, at Pavlo Tychyna Uman State Pedagogical University is oriented towards European trends in the field of secondary education based on the DLL methodology, developed by Goethe-Institute. The essence of this approach lies in the basic principle “Learning to teach German”. For the practically-oriented training of young teachers of the German language, Goethe-Universities direct their efforts in the direction of implementation in the educational process of the materials of the “Learning to teach German” (DLL) program, which is based on the latest theoretical and applied achievements in the field of methods of teaching German as a foreign language and represents innovative approach – research through activity. DLL involves the systematic observation and analysis of academic activities on the basis of video recordings of practical classes in a foreign language in various countries of three continents. Such materials are the basis for a full-fledged analysis of the effectiveness of the lesson and improvement of one’s own professional competences based on a critical analysis of the presented didactic concepts. Each topic is competed with a research project, during which the participant analyzes the lesson in an individually determined aspect and pace. The program covers 12 units of each of the following courses: “German as a Foreign Language” and “German as a Second Foreign Language”.

However, it is worth noting that not all institutions of higher education use the DLL method, and in some of them students of higher education are not even aware of this program.

Another unique opportunity to expand the proposal regarding the individual learning trajectory and development of future foreign language teacher is the CLIL method proposed by Goethe-Institute, the application of which enables teachers to integrate the study

of a foreign language with another educational subject. On the one hand, students study the subject provided by the curriculum, and on the other hand, interesting content motivates them to learn a foreign language and lays the foundation for further independent learning. Therefore, CLIL is, in fact, subject-language integrated learning or study of a professional subject in a foreign language. At the same time, with CLIL, all aspects of language learning are trained, since the educational materials are presented in various formats – text, audio, video.

Having considered the framework conditions and additional opportunities available in Ukraine for the organization and provision of proper training of future teachers of foreign languages, we have conducted a study of its condition by surveying higher education applicants as well as surveying and interviewing teachers. Our goal was to diagnose their awareness and ideas about the essence and structure of readiness for professional activity. It is worth mentioning that the questionnaires contained questions of both closed and open type to reveal more reliable and detailed information. In total, 162 students of higher education took part in the survey.

To the first question of the questionnaire about the availability of professional activity experience, 14% of higher education applicants gave an affirmative answer, who noted that they had already received pedagogical education at college and that they had worked at a school for some time. However, this period did not last long for all of them.

The question “What do you think it means to be ready for professional activity?” (Pic. 1) made it possible to get an idea of the level of awareness of higher education students about the essence, content and features of the professional activity of a foreign language teacher. The answers to this question were quite uniform. The largest number of respondents (43.5%) believe that it is the possession of knowledge (knowledge system), a fairly large share of respondents indicated knowledge and skills (37.1%), and 29.4% had not thought about this question at all and believe that will learn about it when they start working.

Picture 1. What do you think it means to be ready for professional activity?

As for the question “How do you understand the concept of “readiness for professional activity”?” (Pic. 2), the number of respondents was practically divided in half. One half chose the option “availability of knowledge of the disciplines you study at a higher education institution”, and the second – “availability of

practical experience”. Only 12 students of higher education provided detailed answers, indicating that, in addition to knowledge and practical experience, motivation (willingness to work) is also needed.

Picture 2. How do you understand the concept of “readiness for professional activity”?

Answers to the question “How do you understand the concept of “preparation for professional activity”?” (Pic. 3) were, in our opinion, more meaningful, since 72.6% chose an open answer and wrote about the expediency of combining the careful study of the disciplines

of the curriculum and having teaching in general educational institutions, that is, mentioned the two proposed options. The rest (27.4%) provided answers that practically coincided with the answers to the previous question.

Picture 3. How do you understand the concept of “preparation for professional activity”?

The next question was aimed at identifying the sources used by students of higher education and their influence on awareness of the researched problem (Pic. 4). The majority of applicants (59.7%) answered that they had learned about the content of intended professional activities from the Internet, 28.3% – during their teaching practice at school, and only 22.0% – during the study of academic disciplines at the university. This

situation is alarming, because even realizing that young people are used to receiving any information from the Internet, the fact that less than a third of the respondents learned about the content of their intended professional activities at the university, prompts thinking about better informing students in the process of teaching various courses.

Picture 4. The sources used by students of higher education

Our further research involved the analysis of answers to questions about the personal readiness of respondents to carry out professional activities (Pic.5). Most of them (57.4%) believe that they are ready to

work in an educational institution, 29.4% do not know or are not confident in themselves to do so, and 13.2% of the survey participants indicated that they are not ready to work as a foreign language teacher.

Picture 5. The personal readiness of respondents to carry out professional activities

Pertaining to their awareness of the formation of readiness for professional activity (Pic. 6), 47.3% of higher education students consider their knowledge perfect, and 41.2% of respondents are sure that, despite

the sufficient level of knowledge, it needs to be improved. Only 11.5% of applicants rated their knowledge as low.

Picture 6. The level of knowledge of higher education students

In the course of the survey and interview of the teachers, a number of problematic issues were identified, namely:

- lack of methodological recommendations for future teachers of foreign languages regarding self-development both in personal and professional aspects;
- lack of self-control, self-evaluation and self-criticism skills among students of higher education;
- lack of awareness of applicants regarding future professional duties and content of professional activity;
- rather passive attitude of higher education seekers to educational and cognitive activities.

Therefore, the obtained findings of the study indicate the need to improve the professional training of future teachers of foreign languages in the way of considerable improvement of informing them about the essence and content of professional activity as well as focusing on constant self-development and motivation for personal and professional self-improvement.

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